

Ultrasonic and viscometric investigation of albumin protein in aqueous solution

Anjana Mohanty and Sarat K. Swain*

Department of Chemistry, North Orissa University, Takatpur, Baripada-757 003, Orissa, India

E-mail : swainsk2@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-6792-255127

Manuscript received 30 July 2009, accepted 7 September 2009

Abstract : The ultrasonic wave is an efficient powerful and reliable method for various investigations including those of solution dynamics, molecular interactions, miscibility and compatibility of protein in aqueous solution. Ultrasonic velocities and related acoustic parameters were calculated as a function of concentrations of albumin protein in water with a resonance method at frequencies of 3 MHz and 10 MHz. Viscosity (η) of aqueous protein solution was measured by suspended Ubbelohde viscometer. The comparative result of ultrasonic velocities (u), density (ρ), relaxation time (τ), adiabatic compressibility (β_s) and acoustic impedance (z) were studied as a function of the concentrations. The mode of compatibility interaction and miscibility of albumin protein in water were investigated. It was found that the acoustic sound wave perturbed at 3 MHz which explained the weak interaction of water molecule with the segmental motion of albumin protein chains. The interactions of the acoustic result of albumin protein may lead to the development of biomedical active molecules.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, compatibility, relaxation time, acoustic impedance.

Introduction

Albumins are important class of protein, which are important to health and well known component for many organisms¹. A protein classified as albumin is globular protein, that is soluble in water. Globular proteins also have a roughly spherical structure. When combined with water, albumin and other globular proteins form a colloid, a solution which appears homogeneous. The other type of protein, fibrous protein, that found in muscles, which is not water soluble. Within the human body, albumin is an important component of life. In recent years, the application of ultrasonic methods for probing the structural dynamics of biopolymers such as proteins and polysaccharides have been the subject of much research². The studies of ultrasonic absorption of some macromolecules including proteins³, likely to have a contribution from a coupling between the thermal motion of the proteins and water molecules, which changes the strength of their interaction with the protein as a result of its motion. For hemoglobin⁴, protein and dextran, the interaction between solvent and solute is probably the principal mechanism of acoustic absorption^{3,5}. Several workers have used ultrasonic velocity (U) together with

density (ρ) and viscosity (η) measurements to study protein-solvent interactions^{6,7}. In addition, reports have been published on viscometric studies^{8,9} on the interaction and compatibility of protein solutions. However, published reports on compatibility and interaction studies of protein probed by sound velocity and related acoustic parameters are rare^{10,11}. Polymers or biopolymers which are water soluble such as albumin protein have occupied a special area of investigations by researchers through out the globe because of their versatile pharmaceutical, biomedical and industrial applications. These include the preparation of many biomedical products, such as biocompatible hydrogels¹² and anticoagulants¹³ through degradation and grafting onto these proteins. Because of this extensive applicability, we report in this investigation a comparative study of U , related acoustic parameters and viscosity of the pharmaceutically active albumin protein in aqueous solution. Our aim in this paper was to understand the protein-water compatibility and their acoustic properties. Our particular interest in the acoustic properties of this protein was related both to the biomedical applications of ultrasound and to the relevance of the propagation parameters.

Table 1. The comparative values of ultrasonic velocity (U) at frequency of 3 MHz and 10 MHz, density (ρ), viscosity (η), adiabatic compressibility (β_s), acoustic impedance (Z), viscosity relaxation time (τ) for albumin protein at different concentrations (w/v %)

C (w/v %)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg/m ³)	η	$\lambda/2$ (mm)		U (m/s)		$\beta_s \times 10^7$ m ⁻² S ² kg ² .L		Z (SI unit) (min)		$\tau \times 10^7$	
			f	$\lambda/2$	f	U	f	β_s	f	Z	f	τ
			(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)	(MHz)
0	0.9472		3	0.250	3	1500	3	4.70	3	1420.80	3	6.30
			10	0.071	10	1420	10	5.20	10	1345.02	10	7.00
0.1	0.9484	1.063	3	0.252	3	1512	3	4.61	3	1433.98	3	6.53
			10	0.072	10	1440	10	5.08	10	1365.69	10	7.20
0.15	0.9498	1.082	3	0.254	3	1524	3	4.53	3	1447.49	3	6.53
			10	0.073	10	1460	10	4.94	10	1386.71	10	7.12
0.2	0.9525	1.125	3	0.255	3	1530	3	4.48	3	1457.32	3	6.72
			10	0.075	10	1500	10	4.66	10	1428.77	10	6.99
0.25	0.9540	1.165	3	0.257	3	1542	3	4.40	3	1471.06	3	7.05
			10	0.077	10	1540	10	4.41	10	1469.16	10	6.86
0.3	0.9563	1.20	3	0.259	3	1554	3	4.33	3	1486.09	3	6.92
			10	0.079	10	1580	10	4.18	10	1510.95	10	6.70

Experimental

Albumin bovine protein sample was supplied by the SISCO Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. The sample was used without further purification. The pH of the supplied sample was 6.0–7.0. The water used for the experiments was doubly distilled over alkaline permanganate and deionized. An ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, India) is a simple digital monitoring and direct device to determine the ultrasonic velocity in liquids with a high degree of accuracy (± 0.001). The principle used in the measurement of velocity (U) is based on the accurate determination of the wavelength (λ) in the medium. Ultrasonic waves of known frequency (f) are produced by a quartz plate fixed at the bottom of the cell. The waves are reflected by a movable metallic plate kept parallel to the quartz plate. If the separation between these plates is exactly a whole multiple of the sound wavelength, standing waves are formed in the medium. Ultrasonic velocity measurements were performed at frequencies of 3 MHz and 10 MHz. We made the measurements by varying the concentration (C) of albumin protein at temperature of 30 °C. The viscosity (η) of the sample solution was measured at 30 °C with a Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. The density (ρ)

of the sample solution was determined with a specific gravity bottle of 25 ml capacity. The ultrasonic acoustic parameters were calculated with the standard formulas¹⁴ as follows.

Ultrasonic velocity (U):

If the distance is increased or decreased and the variation exactly one half wavelength ($\lambda/2$) or multiple of it, anode current again becomes maximum.

$$U = \lambda \times f$$

where λ = wavelength in mm and f = frequency in MHz.

Adiabatic compressibility (β_s):

$$\beta_s = 1/\rho U^2$$

where ρ = density and U = ultrasonic velocity.

Acoustic impedance (Z):

$$Z = \rho \times U$$

where ρ = density and U = ultrasonic velocity.

Viscosity relaxation time (τ):

$$\tau = 4\eta/3\rho U^2$$

where ρ = density and U = ultrasonic velocity.

Fig. 1. Variation of ultrasonic velocities with concentration in aqueous solutions of albumin protein.

Fig. 2. Variation of adiabatic compressibility with concentration in aqueous solutions of albumin protein.

Results and discussion

The value of ultrasonic velocity (U) viscosity (η) and density (ρ) of serum albumin protein are summarized in Table 1. To understand the structural effect and molecular interaction occurring in aqueous solution of albumin protein, we derived several acoustic and thermodynamical parameters from different experimental results of ultrasonic velocity, viscosity and density. It is found that, density of albumin protein increases gradually with increasing concentration of the solution, from 0.1–0.3 (w/v)%.

Viscosities of albumin protein progressively increased with variation of concentration. It is noticed that viscosity of the solution increased by 15% with increasing concentration 0.1–0.3 (w/v)%. Increase in viscosity with the raise of concentration may be due to the enhanced tendency of protein molecules to associate in the protein-water system.

Ultrasonic velocities were measured at different frequencies of ultrasound i.e. 3 MHz and 10 MHz with variation of concentration of the solution. In both the frequency, ultrasonic velocities were increased gradually with increased concentration. However, increase of velocity at low frequency i.e. 3 MHz is proportionally less than the velocity at high frequency. That means the plot at frequency of 10 MHz is stiffer as compared to the velocity at 3 MHz (Fig. 1). This may be due to active

interaction of concentration with the aqueous solution of albumin protein. The protein chain may have hindered rotation or conformational interconversion that occurred at high frequency of sound wave. At all concentrations, the velocities vary almost linearly, which indicated the compatible nature of protein in aqueous solution.

The protein chain assumes a variety of conformational changes under different experimental conditions. Protein chains are more compressible because of their chain like structure, which can be shown by a decrease in adiabatic compressibility with increase in concentration (Fig. 2). This result was verified at both frequencies of ultrasound (3 MHz and 10 MHz) with different values of concentration.

Comparing the results at frequency of 3 MHz and 10 MHz, we assume that the acoustic sound wave perturbed at 3 MHz, the segmental motion of albumin protein chain in such a way as to cause rearrangement of the water molecule weakly interacting with the protein chain. This result was in good agreement with the result obtained due to the ultrasonic relaxation in aqueous solution of dextran³ and PV A-dextran blending¹¹.

The acoustic impedance (Z) of albumin protein increased linearly with increase in concentration at both frequencies of ultrasound. The increasing trend of Z with concentration could be interpreted on the basis that most of the solvent molecule were engaged in interaction with them by cross linking via hydrogen bond and were compatible in all range of concentrations.

Fig. 3. Variation of viscosity relaxation time with concentration in aqueous solutions of albumin protein.

The variation of τ with concentration is plotted in Fig. 3. It is found that viscosity relaxation time decreased linearly with concentration at ultrasonic frequency of 10 MHz. But at low ultrasonic frequency of 3 MHz, τ increased with concentration up to 0.25 (w/v)% and then decreased with further increase of the concentration. The result is evident that the interaction and compatibility of water-protein solution were prominent via structural change due to entropy fluctuation.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by Department of Science and Technology, Government of India (Funding Ref. DST/SR/FTP/CS-130/2006).

References

1. Fennema and M. Dekker, *J. Food Chemistry Aminoacids, Peptides and Proteins*, 1905, 5, 245.
2. R. B. Gregory and M. Dekker, *J. Protein-Solvent Interaction*, 1995, 15, 340.
3. S. Kato, T. Suzuki, H. Nomura and Y. Miyahara, *J. Macromolecules*, 1980, 13, 889.
4. E. L. Carstensen and H. P. Schwan, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 1959, 31, 305.
5. S. A. Hawley and F. Dunn, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, 50, 3523.
6. W. Bell and R. A. Pethrick, *J. Eur. Polym.*, 1972, 8, 827.
7. E. Tsushida and K. Abe, *Interaction Between Macromolecule in Solution and Intermolecular Complexes*, 1982, 35, 218.
8. W. H. Jiang and S. J. Han, *J. Eur. Polym.*, 1998, 34, 1571.
9. R. Garcia, O. Melad, C. M. Gomez, J. E. Figuerullo and A. Campos, *J. Eur. Polym.*, 1999, 35, 47.
10. O. Olabisi, L. M. Robenson and M. T. Shaw, *In Polymer-Polymer Miscibility*, 1979, 35, 784.
11. P. K. Sahoo, R. Mohapatra, A. Sahoo and S. K. Swain, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2003, 88, 3196.
12. W. N. E. Dijk-Wolthuis, S. K. Y. Tsang, J. J. K. Bosch and W. K. Hennink, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1997, 38, 6235.
13. R. K. Samal, P. K. Sahoo, S. S. Ray and S. N. Nayak, *J. Macromol. Chem.*, 1985, 11, 129.
14. P. S. Nikam and M. I. Hasan, *J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1990, 28, 197.